

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF SOWING RATES ON VEGETATIVE PARAMETERS OF “QISMƏT” TRITICALE VARIETY

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Abstract

The purpose of the research work is to study the productivity indicators of triticale plants under different sowing rates and plant densities in the soil-climatic conditions of the Ganja-Dashkasan region and to determine the optimal cultivation parameters. The object of the research work is the “Qismət” triticale variety. The subject of the research work is the impact of agrotechnical factors such as plant density and sowing rates on the development of triticale plants, yield elements and total grain yield. The research work was carried out in the experimental field at the “Grain and Legume” plants field laboratory of ASAU in 2024-2026. The field experiment was carried out using the classical precise sowing method, applying different sowing rates (3.5; 4; 4.5; 5 million seeds/ha) and plant densities. During the research, the productivity and biomorphological indicators of triticale plants under different sowing rates and plant densities will be analyzed comparatively. The results obtained will allow for the scientific determination of optimal triticale cultivation schemes in regional conditions. As a result of the research, the optimal sowing rate and plant density of triticale in regional conditions will be determined. This will allow for the provision of scientifically based recommendations to farmers and specialists working in the agricultural sector. The results obtained will serve to increase triticale productivity, reduce production costs and ensure agro-ecological sustainability.

Keywords: triticale, sowing rate, germination, survival rate, plant height, productive tillering.

Triticale is a new plant developed through the hybridization of wheat and rye. Breeding programs for triticale have been carried out and are ongoing in many countries, primarily in the USA, Poland, Canada, and Mexico. These studies aim to increase productivity per acre in nutritionally poor agricultural areas and thereby help meet the food demands of the rapidly growing global population. In triticale research, wheat is used as the maternal plant and rye as the paternal plant. Triticale's adaptability and productivity in arid regions come from wheat, while its ability to grow in cold, acidic, and saline soils is inherited from rye [5,7].

In areas where wheat and barley cannot be grown with high quality due to unfavorable soil conditions, triticale demonstrates a higher yield potential. Compared to wheat and barley, triticale is more tolerant to both nutritional and non-nutritional stress conditions. Globally, triticale is primarily used as a grain crop for animal feed. It is also cultivated for forage production and as pasture for livestock. Triticale is widely used as a grain source in poultry feed, with a feed quality comparable to that of maize, wheat, and barley. Of the three million hectares of triticale cultivated worldwide, approximately 80% is sown in the fall and 20% in the spring. In recent years, triticale flour mixed with high-quality wheat flour has also been used in the production of baked goods, cookies, bread, cakes, and pasta [6,11].

There are a total of 4.2 million hectares of triticale cultivation area worldwide. Of this, 80% is used for winter triticale cultivation, while 20% is for spring cultivation. The global average yield of triticale is 364 kg per day. In terms of cultivated area, Poland, Belarus, Germany, and France rank among the top producers. Globally, around 266,000 tons of triticale are exported,

while 221,000 tons are imported [10].

As the world population continues to grow, food production must increase at the same pace. With arable land reaching its limit, scientists have been driven to achieve higher yields per unit area using existing crops, as well as to introduce new plant species capable of producing acceptable yields on poor soils and under various environmental stresses. Triticale, a hybrid of wheat and rye, is one of the first and most successful outcomes of such research. Globally, especially in developed countries, triticale is cultivated on approximately 2.9 million hectares. Of the total cultivated area, 80% is used for winter triticale and 20% for spring triticale [8].

Cereal crops such as wheat, barley, oats, rye, and triticale are primarily grown for their grains and used as human food, but they are also harvested for fodder and used as roughage feed. In the rest of the world, the use of cereals as animal feed is widespread. The feed obtained from these grains is given to animals in fresh, dried, or silaged for [1].

High-quality roughage production plays a key role in the development of forage crops and the livestock industry. However, feed and feeding costs, which make up a significant portion (60–70%) of the production stage in livestock farming, have a considerable impact on business profitability. In recent years, the use of cereal crops as green fodder within forage production has also been increasing proportionally [2].

Triticale is a hybrid plant species, artificially created by humans, that represents a new botanical genus within the Poaceae family. It combines the beneficial traits of both wheat and rye. Progress in the breeding and cultivation of winter triticale depends on

the existing genetic diversity, the method of incorporating desirable genes into superior genotypes, and the efficiency of selected genotypes and lines [3, 4, 9, 12].

In our experiment, the field germination of the "Qismət" variety according to the seeding rate variants was as follows: 63.6–79%, 74.8–81.7%, and 75.3–83.7%. Our data align with existing literature: as the seeding rate increases, the survival rate of plants decreases. At the same time, crops with high seeding rates thin out significantly.

According to Table 1, the highest germination percentage for the "Qismət" triticale variety was observed at a seeding rate of 3.5 million seeds/ha. Increasing the seeding rate from 3.5 to 5.0 million seeds/ha reduced germination capacity by approximately 8.6% (from 81.5% to 72.9%). Notably, when the seeding rate increased by 42% (from 3.5 to 5.0 million seeds/ha), the number of plants only increased by 28% (from 285 to 367 plants/m²). This indicates that the yield gained from each additional kilogram of seed sown decreases progressively. At a seeding rate of 5.0 million seeds/ha, the plant density reached its highest level (367 plants/m²). However, this density may negatively affect plant height growth and grain filling in the future, as the plants begin to shade each other. Thus, the conclusion is that the highest quality germination (percentage-wise) occurs at 3.5 million seeds/ha, while the highest quantity (number of plants) is achieved at 5.0 million seeds/ha.

As seen in Table 1, when the seeding rate is high (for example, 5.0 million seeds/ha), plant density in the field increases. As a result, competition for water, nutrients, and sunlight intensifies among plants, leading to the death of weaker plants. In dense sowings, air

circulation weakens and moisture accumulates, increasing the risk of disease spread and thus reducing the survival rate. There is a 7.4% difference in survival rate (60.3% - 52.9%) between the sparsest seeding rate (3.5 million seeds/ha) and the densest seeding rate (5.0 million seeds/ha).

Looking at Table 1, despite increasing the seeding rate from 3.5 to 5.0 million (approximately 43%), the number of surviving plants only increased by 10.9% (from 174 to 193). This indicates that a large portion of the additional sown seeds is wasted. Nature itself regulates the density in the field. Although extra sown seeds may germinate, they cannot withstand competition during the growth period and die off. The 5.0 million seeds/ha rate requires higher costs (for seeds), but the number of plants remaining in the field does not differ significantly compared to the 3.5 million seeds/ha rate (the difference is only 19 plants/m²).

Based on the figures given in Table 1, analyzing the effect of seeding rates on the plant height of the "Qismət" triticale variety shows that plant height decreases as the seeding rate increases. This can be explained by several factors: 1. Reduction of nutrient area – As the seeding rate rises, the nutrient area available per plant decreases. This leads to weaker development of the root system and consequently the above-ground parts (height) of the plant. 2. Light and competition – In dense plantings, plants shade each other. The decrease in height from 139 cm to 131 cm indicates that excessive density hinders plants from reaching their full height potential. 3. Durability – Usually, taller plants (in sparse planting) have stronger stems. In very dense plantings, plants tend to be shorter and have weaker stem development.

Table 1. Effect of seeding rates on vegetative traits of "Qismət" triticale variety

Variants Seeding rates mln. seeds/ha	Seed germination rate	Number of germinated plants	Plant survival rate	Number of surviving plants	Plant height	Productive tillering
3,5	81,5	285	60,3	174	139	1,68
4,0	78,9	313	58,4	186	135	1,62
4,5	75,1	334	55,7	189	133	1,59
5,0	72,9	367	52,9	193	131	1,39

Table 1 also shows the effect of seeding rates on the total number of productive tillers per 1 m² in the "Qismət" triticale variety. This indicator reflects the field's final potential as a synthesis of both the seeding rate and the tillering capacity. It is evident from the table that increasing the seeding rate affects the number of productive stems per 1 m² in a nonlinear manner. The highest number of productive ears (stems) in the field was obtained at the seeding rate of 4.0 mln/ha. In this variant, the balance between the number of plants and the individual tillering capacity created the highest yield potential. When the seeding rate reached 5.0 mln/ha, the number of productive tillers sharply decreased to 267. This means that due to excessive density, some plants cannot produce productive stems or wither from weakness. Notably, at the 5.0 mln/ha variant, although more seeds were sown, the result

(267) was even lower than at the sparsest seeding (293). This proves that excessive density directly causes yield loss.

From our research, we can conclude that as the seeding rate increases, the germination capacity and the number of germinated plants tend to decrease. The survival rate is inversely proportional to the seeding rate, meaning that as the seeding rate increases, the survival rate decreases. Although the number of surviving plants increases, plant height decreases with increasing seeding rate. Productive tillering shows better results at lower seeding rates. Overall, it is evident that the optimal seeding rate is strategically important for achieving high germination and survival rates as well as increased yield.

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